

Robustness of Commissioned Coordinated Q–V Controller for Multi-machine Power Plant

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What did we do?

- We presented commissioning details of a coordinated reactive power-voltage controller (CQVC) installed in a multi-machine steam power plant (SPP).
- The CQVC regulates reactive power and voltage of a 1992MVA multi-machine SPP.
- Once commissioned the CQVC performance under various operating conditions is assessed in order to assure correct CQVC response (action).

The Outline

- Why did we do it? (Motivation)
- How did we do it? (Methodology)
- What did we get? (The Results)
- What did we learn? (Conclusions)

Why did we do it?

- Intra-plant reactive power-voltage (Q-V) coordination implies reactive power (Q) allocation among participating generators in accordance to their reactive power capabilities while continuously maintaining an HV busbar voltage and supplying reactive power to the system as requested by the system operator.
- The allocation of Q in accordance to generator curve capability limits.
- The intra-plant Q-V controller starts to act after the initial transient has subsided.
- The reactive power control during the transients remains exclusively the responsibility of the existing AVR. I

Why did we do it?

The following issues needed to be addressed prior to full deployment of the CQVC:

- Tune the CQVC parameters;
- Identify the CQVC's sensitivity to changes in system parameters;
- Estimate the on-line generator reactive capability (including coordination with excitation limiters and protection);
- Identify the CQVC sensitivity to extreme network conditions (e.g., peak or light loading).

Daily variation in available reactive power

Variation in Q_{\min} available from units A1 (red trace) and A2 (blue trace) during the 24h cycle, according to active power and capability charts.

Typically applied D-diagram

$$P = \tan \delta_{\max} \cdot Q + \tan \delta_{\max} \frac{V^2}{X} = aQ + b$$

$$S_{\max}^2 = P^2 + Q^2 = (VI_{\max}^2)$$

$$P^2 + \left(Q + \frac{V^2}{X}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{E_{\max}V}{X}\right)^2$$

SG's capability diagram for rated stator terminal voltage,
with SG saturation neglected

Factors affecting reactive power delivered to the system

- Reactive power consumed within power plant (by local loads)
- Reactive power losses in the step-up transformer
- Generator terminal voltage.

Limitations imposed by exploitation conditions

Constraints influencing SG's operating range:

- HV busbar voltage
 - the ISO tries to maintain voltages at certain network buses so it is more straightforward to refer D-diagram to HV busbar voltage than to ever-changing SG terminal voltage,
- SG saturation
 - SG terminal voltage change causes the move of the rotor current limit (this move in opposite direction depending whether saturation is taken into account or not),
- Step-up transformer reactance and Q flow,
- Voltage range of auxiliary equipment supplied from the SG transformer.

How did we do it?

- New limits Q_{min} and Q_{max} are super imposed over the original D-diagram.
- Available measurements are (P, Q, V_{HV}) .
- Since in this case, the generator terminal voltages exceeded permissible voltage range ($\pm 5\%$ of the rated voltage) when the total Q was uniformly distributed according to the D-diagrams, new boundaries had to be calculated.
- For permissible V_{tmin} and V_{tmax} new Q_{min} and Q_{max} limits are calculated as follows:

$$Q_{i\ min/max} = (V_{t\ min/max} - V_{HV})V_{HV}/X_i$$

Q redistribution due to change in V_{t1max}

Robustness of CQVC

Detailed analysis of the robustness of the sensitivity matrix (implemented in the CQVC) to changes in external parameters was carried out.

To determine the necessary change in voltage reference in order to achieve the desired Q changes, the inverse of the sensitivity matrix is used:

$$[\Delta|E_i|] = [S]^{-1} [\Delta Q_i]$$

Following approximation of full sensitivity matrix is used:

$$[S]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} X_{net} + X_1 & X_{net} & X_{net} & X_{net} \\ X_{net} & X_{net} + X_2 & X_{net} & X_{net} \\ X_{net} & X_{net} & X_{net} + X_3 & X_{net} \\ X_{net} & X_{net} & X_{net} & X_{net} + X_4 \end{bmatrix}$$

CQVC sensitivity to change in parameters

CQVC operation with changed X_{droop} of A1 AVR

- The robustness of the controller to single parameter change.
- X_{droop} of the AVR at unit A1 was changed, X_1 was changed from 0.1695 p.u. to 0.106 p.u. (37.5%)
- CQVC was sending unnecessary commands to AVRs.
- The overall stable operation of the CQVC was never endangered and there was no error in plant Q and voltage control.

CQVC Sensitivity to network disturbances

Sensitivity of the CQVC to large and fast network perturbations as well as its non-interference with the excitation system response are addressed next.

CQVC and AVR's SGs response at single phase fault at 220kV transmission line

Immediately after the fault, as soon as the AVR's action has subsided, the CQVC tries and succeeds in restoring the $V_{HV200kV}$ within acceptable boundaries of the pre fault value without violation of any limits.

CQVC Sensitivity to light loading condition

The maximum/minimum reactive power ($Q_{HV}^{\max/\min}$) is the power that for certain operating conditions could be delivered/absorbed from the SPP:

$$Q_{HV}^{\max} = \Sigma Q_i^{\max}, \quad Q_{HV}^{\min} = \Sigma Q_i^{\min}$$

The SPP Q-V characteristic under the CQVC (white area).

Network characteristics X_{net} :

- Light loading conditions blue
- Peak loading conditions red
- Natural plant characteristics ($X_{droop_Natural}$) green

The shadowed areas denote the operating conditions in which SG limitations are reached.

Conclusions

- Brief theoretical background on CQVC design is presented.
- Details on commissioning of CQVC, coordination with unit SCADA, practical design specifications are given.
- Methodology for online evaluation of available reactive power of individual generators in the plant is developed.

The robustness of the controller was also shown to provide appropriate Q-V control for the plant even when the plant parameters were significantly changed from those used at design stage of the controller, and when the plant was exposed to large network disturbances and extreme operating conditions.

Power system benefits from CQVC installation

Methodology for on-line evaluation of available reactive power of individual generators in the plant enables:

- Independent System Operator real time insight into the actually available Q capability of each generator to support HV bus voltage.

- Q reserves of SPP are kept at max.

Conclusions